

Navigating TechCentral's Startup Ecosystem: Commercialisation and Capital

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

In urban planning terms, Sydney CBDs have long stood at the apex of the activity centre hierarchy. They are key nodes of consumption for the services, hospitality and retail sectors (Mortimer, 2020). Apart from that, Sydney CBD is a centre of employment and academic institutions, where the EE could unleash all the vitality contained in work, knowledge, technology, management and capital and give full play to all sources of social wealth for the benefit of the people.

Cetindamar, Lammers & Zhang (2020) suggested that new knowledge presents opportunities for commercial value and can hence be a critical asset for EE's. The people, skills, knowledge that gathered in Sydney CBD has long shaped the state of its EE as a central hub of technology and innovation.

However, the arrival of COVID-19 had a dramatic impact on CBD-dominant local government areas, which badly affected the development of its entrepreneur ecosystem under this global pandemic. As a result of COVID-19 cases spiking, CBD workers, especially casuals, are losing their jobs, while large numbers of office-based CBD workers have to work from home. IN that sense, the Sydney CBD has to evolve to another state in a sense of 'New Normal' under which more than 70% of people want to split their post-pandemic time between private life and remote working (PwC, 2021).

This might push Tech Central's key stakeholders to figure out a more efficient way to collaborate under such conditions. NSW Executive Director of the Property Council of Australia Jane Fitzgerald said that 'Sydney CBD's vibrancy relies on workers being able to return to their offices and re-engage with their peers' (2021). This view will shape the EE of Sydney CBD towards re-embracing face-to-face collaboration, as one of the policy makers of the EE suggested the main goal of the current ecosystem is to get more people back to CBD.

In that sense, key industry bodies in the Sydney CBD will join forces to invest in CBD activation, attracting more workers back to the CBD. For example, upon building up, Tech Central might provide enticing technology and social events to proactively encourage Sydney CBD workers to back into the office. It is a critical part of the overall plan to re-liven the EE, thus far re-building the State's economy post-pandemic.

To better understand how key stakeholders have shaped the EE state in the past and now, three of the main accelerators that are based in the CBD BlueChilli, Sydney Startup hub and Tech Central. These accelerators have played an important role in the development of innovation and startups. They have had a direct impact on the Entrepreneurial ecosystem of the CBD and they as well as other accelerators and anchor tenants will continue to shape the ecosystem with the NSW Government focusing on innovation and new technology.

1.1 BlueChilli

BlueChilli is considered Australia's most successful start-up accelerators (2019 Financial Review), with currently three different active accelerator programs that focus on three different fields of innovation. These programs include SheStarts, a venture-backed startup program for women entrepreneurs in the technology industry, BlueChilli Healthtech that aims to improve health outcomes in Southeast Asia and Future Minds Accelerator, a program aimed at preparing Australian youths for the future of work. The nature of these accelerator programs gives startups the opportunity to solve problems that are best suited to their field.

Originally, Blue Chilli was solely an Australia based project that collaborated with Australian startups. However, with the launch of the accelerator program BlueChilli HealthTech based in Singapore to focus on the Southeast Asian health outcomes as well as having a corporate intrapreneurship program in Indonesia, they have branched out to international partnerships. This allows for a more diverse team with different perspectives that can identify various challenges and solutions.

1.2 Sydney Startup Hub

Sydney Startup Hub is a place for accelerators and startups to come to work with other entrepreneurs, network and to gain invaluable advice and potential business investments. Start-ups like this have helped the community to grow and play a vital role within the entrepreneurial ecosystem. It is a crucial innovation centre that has played a vital role in making Sydney Australia's startup capital. Being home to accelerators

such as The Studio, Tank Stream Labs, Fishburners, Antler Australia and Stone & Chalk as well as 2,500 residents under these accelerators, Sydney Startup Hub has created over 1,000 jobs and has attracted over \$280 million in investment. With over 40% of startups in Australia are created in NSW, Sydney Startup Hub has had a major impact on the success of the CBD Entrepreneurial Ecosystem.

1.3 Tech Central

Tech Central is set to be developed in the CBD Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, next to Central Station thus will become the epicentre of Sydney's innovation and technology community. The addition of Tech Central will significantly change the ecosystem and set in motion the future of the CBD Entrepreneurial Ecosystem with 25000 jobs that focus on education, science, mathematics and technology expected to be created by 2035. It will also house some of the country's leading technology companies. With this focus on technology and innovation, Tech Central has been dubbed as Australia's Silicon Valley, thus demonstrating the influence it will have on the CBD Entrepreneurial Ecosystem as well as Sydney as a whole. This has been in motion since 2016 when Central Precinct was nominated as a state significant precinct by Transport for NSW and then declared by the Minister for planning as nominated state significant precinct.

2 Ecosystem Map

2.1 Overview

The map is presented in the form of circular ripples extending further out from each other, initiating in the inner circumference with the industries and stakeholders that directly engage with the ecosystem and form the moving parts that allow it to possess its dynamic nature. As the ripples extend further outwards, the map demonstrates how the front-facing industries interact with other small and large businesses to continue to improve and innovate their services. Through such, the "ripple effect" of consistent collaborations between multiple bodies and impact of such collaborations between stakeholders in the ecosystem is presented through the structure of the map. While most ecosystems demonstrate connections between stakeholders through lines and arrows, ripples encompass the impact of various innovation, regulatory and government organisations as an influence on all systems within the EE.

2.2 Why include these features in the mapping?

The presentation of the map as a series of circular rims were designed to represent the degree to which each of the stakeholders directly impact the functioning and ultimate expansion of the ecosystem. The further inwards the circular rim is, the more directly they are involved with the ecosystem and its evolution. The exploration of unique industries was also differentiated to highlight the multiple areas of specialty which can be innovated within the Sydney CBD area and therefore the capabilities of the EE to foster new entrepreneurial concepts. For the purpose of Assessment 2, the industries on the map are a collective of the industries explored in Assessment 1, however there are currently a range of additional industries operating within the EE including the technology, science and creative industries. The division of the map into quarters is also integrated into the design to imitate the format of a navigation system; reinforcing the idea that the ecosystem can always be explored for something new to enhance existing understandings and methods of practice. It depicts a metaphor whereby entrepreneurial businesses continuously emerge and populate the EE.

2.3 What does this say about the ecosystem?

In initially interpreting the map, the ecosystem is depicted as an area or precinct within which there are a multitude of large and small corporations as well as varying levels of governance; as one would observe within a small community. However when observed further, it can be recognised that each stakeholder is ultimately dependent, directly or indirectly, on another in terms of its ability to meet multifaceted user and societal expectations; with new interactions constantly forming and potential connections manifesting, demonstrating the ecosystem's dynamic nature and the need for different organisations in different industries to be able to rely on and collaborate with each other to successfully continue to function as an active part of the ecosystem. It indicates that industries with different specialties interact together to strengthen the capabilities of their products and services, ultimately innovating to remain competitive. The structure of the map also suggests the place of global organisations as one that is important to the increasing development of the ecosystem. The further-most outer rim of the map where potential international collaborators are listed highlight areas where the Sydney CBD's EE can benefit from a global presence operating within the local area in the future, while sustaining the concept of collaborative innovation strategies as a primary trait in allowing the ecosystem to continue to thrive.

2.4 How will the map be affected by growth and change in the future?

As the ecosystem grows and Tech Central becomes an established and credible entrepreneurial district, the number of corporations, small businesses and innovation hubs will likely increase and diversify the ecosystem, whilst new industries that don't yet exist may emerge; enhancing the density of the ecosystem through representations on the map. Due to the future expansion of the EE, the overall scale of the map is also likely to extend, developing new "ripples" as new classifications of stakeholders emerge within the ecosystem. The enhancement of detail available in the future mapping, in addition to the new stakeholders and industries included in the EE, will also likely create an opportunity for more specific, nuanced connections to become established between local and international stakeholders and therefore, offer greater understandings of how interactions between them benefit each individual stakeholder as well as the overall EE. It is also important to note that while these changes result in modifications of the visualisation within the scope of the existing mapping system, large changes that disrupt the ecosystem and change the way in which businesses engage with the resources available to them may result in a complete structural change of the map to accommodate to the advanced EE system.

2.5 What are the strengths and weaknesses of the current map?

2.5.1 Strengths

The map is a useful tool to determine how different aspects of the ecosystem are connected and the way they function to ensure the ecosystem achieves its purpose in providing an innovative space for entrepreneurs and businesses to prosper. More specifically, the map classifies the different industries and influential figures contributing to the ecosystem and future Tech Central space, enabling viewers to clearly and easily interpret where each stakeholder exists within the EE as well as providing an idea of how they can approach or be approached by others in the EE in the process of collaborative opportunities. The map is thereby also able to indicate how each organisation in the ecosystem is relevant to the growth of the precinct as well as highlighting the specific role it plays, allowing future potential connections to be identified and capitalised on from a forecasted perspective and a forward- thinking approach by current establishments in the EE.

2.5.2 Areas for Improvement

The map, though displaying a strength in remaining clearly decisive of how varying stakeholders fit in the ecosystem, may also become an area for improvement as the ecosystem expands. In the instance where additional stakeholders join the EE, the classifications may make it difficult to present overlaps in stakeholder areas of specialty in different industries, or grey areas regarding how organisations impact the EE. The emergence of a Tech company developing equipment specialising in the medical field, for instance, may be difficult to find a place for on the map as it occupies two industries under IT and health. The possibility of a difficulty in reading and interpreting the map as it grows is also likely as the concise

features are overcome by the growing number of connections and interactions between organisations. The definitive establishment of where Tech Central exists once it opens would also create a need for a presentation of the geographic proximity of the organisations within the ecosystem, which the current map is unable to do.

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 Big Why and What

While an exciting development, the announcement of Tech-central by no means guarantees success for Sydney's entrepreneurial ecosystem. The project undoubtedly brings a level of physical infrastructure that is much needed but consistent with the Brookings Innovation District Report; physical assets are just one-third of the type of physical infrastructure required to create an effective innovation district (Katz & Wagner, 2014).

Moreover, in terms of physical infrastructure, it is unclear whether, through the development of Tech-Central other physical infrastructure assets such as transportation will improve or worsen.

Thus, we acknowledge there are several areas in which future growth can be achieved. Though for this report, we will prioritise some more than others. Generally, we visualise future success as being defined by the degree to which stakeholders are interconnected. Early on, we think such a connection can be fostered by government initiatives curbed at attracting investors both locally and abroad by incentivising investment into start-ups in their early stages (Appendix 1).

Similarly, an increase in mission-orientated challenges initiated by industry and government should be directed across the broader ecosystem to allow students and young start-ups a chance at providing solutions (Appendix 1). In essence, we see these initiatives aimed at creating formal networks will be essential to growing human talent, economic development, and creating collaborative relationships by which future innovation can be built.

Remaining mindful of the areas prioritised throughout this proposal, the visualisation of the ecosystem presented below is likely to become more populated and diverse in comparison to the ecosystem map explored above.

3.1.1 Visualisation of the future EE

(See next page)

Legend:

-
 More government involvement in supporting small businesses and startups by becoming directly involved in the innovation space and providing additional funding, special capacity and international collaboration opportunities
-
 More international businesses moving inwards on the map to support Australian small businesses and startups, while also potentially establishing a branch in Sydney within the EE
-
 Additional international organisations to become involved in the Tech Central EE
-
 New innovation hubs and startups will emerge as a result of the additional support available
-
 Additional sources of capital and financial support for innovative thinkers
-
 Additional networking and collaboration events to be hosted to appeal to businesses and individuals and promote an engagement with the entrepreneurial environment and innovate
-
 The concepts of "Innovation" and "Entrepreneurship" to become more prominent topics to focus on and invest in throughout educational institutions and the workplace

3.2 Lever 1

Through extensive desk-based research and interactions with several key stakeholders within the Ultimo-Camperdown ecosystem, it has become apparent that the commercialisation of university research will be an important area in which future growth can be realised. We would recommend it is inherent that Universities initiate and improve their own Technology Transfer Offices (TTO's), which are common among Universities in North America and Europe but rare in Australia (Appendix 1) (Ketchell, 2021). Higher education research funding prior to COVID-19 were primarily contributions from within the University exceeding State and Federal Government support by nearly 3 billion dollars, which has only worsened in the aftermath of the global pandemic (Ketchell, 2021). Bercovitz & Feldman (2006) states that many universities across the world have realigned research activities to be more consistent with the needs of the industry in which they operate – for instance, specialized research units, joint ventures, or interdisciplinary projects that are more responsive to industry needs. These are particularly initiatives of interest to Universities to the Sydney EE, due to their potential to attract funding as well as creating desired outcomes for government and industry.

The first activator and perhaps most important in improving what is referred to as academic entrepreneurship is Government. Director of the Sydney Knowledge Hub at The University of Sydney, Rupal Ismi, suggests several initiatives at the government level that can support the commercialisation of research. These can include funding contracts that deliver real- world needs, providing Universities with incentives to help researchers commercialise their work, and giving investors incentives to fund in the early stage where it is most risky. While government stakeholders may be hesitant to direct more funds into improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem, some considerations must be made. While state funding and subsidies will be needed for University TTO's to improve, the scheme will have the potential to become self-sufficient as the TTO's grow and develop (Bessant & Rush, 1995). Further, without subsidies, TTO's who are entirely self-funding may be aligned to achieve results purely based on financial output, which doesn't always spur economic development. For instance, highly resourceful firms may license or patent technology only to suppress it. Thus, to achieve the most favourable outcomes, government support should be consistent and unwavering.

As the second key activator in this space, it is important that Universities recognise the incessant need for them to be more responsive to the needs of society. Faculty Research Engagement Manager Dr Alex Thomson at UTS, suggested that researchers possess a willingness to want to contribute to societal problems. Further adding that Universities were actively attempting to guide Ph.D. students to commit to attaining industry experience and studying entrepreneurial-related subjects, an idea Sydney Knowledge Hub Director Rupal Ismi is in favour of. Consistent with both Thomson and Ismi we suggest this would be a helpful intervention as it provides students with industry knowledge as well as providing industry partners with highly skilled individuals who can help collect data (Appendix 1).

As argued by Powers & Mcdougall (2005), the propensity of investment by industry into University research fosters an entrepreneurial spirit from within the university while simultaneously creating new relationships by which future collaboration can be built. Thus, we see the success of the commercialisation of University research as being highly correlated to the degree by which the network of above activators continues to become more interconnected. Further, successful outcomes will not only be reciprocally beneficial to the above network of activators but to the EE and society as a whole.

3.3 Lever 2

The vision statement for the entrepreneurial ecosystem in the next ten years is to create an enabling entrepreneurship environment whereby every participant has quick access to finance and starts of effective and productive business with a lot of ease. The entrepreneurial ecosystem is composed of some major aspects, including the banking system, investment system, among other trading activities. Notably, the above vision can be achieved by increasing the level of training through creativity in the entrepreneurial sector (Cao et al.,2021). The creativity in regards to the current technology is constructive to the business environment for smooth operation. It is achieved through the focus of the training agencies to embrace digitalization, which comes with many opportunities for almost all the stakeholders in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. From the interviews regarding the university sector, the universities are key stakeholders in the entrepreneurial contribution since they train scholars who are well equipped in the current technology to venture into the entrepreneurial sector.

From the analysis of the current entrepreneurial ecosystem, there are numerous opportunities that should be exploited to create and empower the entrepreneurial ecosystem sector. For instance, one of the opportunities which need exploitation is the vast skills and knowledge from the university products (students). The students themselves are opportunities in the market that can be made use of to create a

productive entrepreneurial ecosystem (Cao et al.,2021). Many of the students from the Australian universities are equipped with useful skills and knowledge in the financial sector plus the technology to help improve the entrepreneurial ecosystem. Another opportunity is entrepreneurial recycling, which means recycling the wealth created by successful entrepreneurs and their associated learning.

Successful entrepreneurs are rich in skills and experience in terms of the business. Therefore, the skills should be recycled through training the young staff on the modalities and the logistics of productive entrepreneurship.

The following key stakeholders will be directly or indirectly involved in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. The University of Technology Sydney has played and still playing an important role in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. It is through the intensive research and the production of well-skilled and knowledge-equipped students to enhance creativity and innovation in the entrepreneurial sector (Spigel et al.,2018). Secondly is the Atlens law firm, which is useful in terms of the legal industry sector. It makes sure that the proper legal channels and the problem related to the law matters are well taken care of. Finally, is the board of directors for the Australian bank, which has continually pumped enormous amounts of cash in the entrepreneurial sector.

There are some parameters that should be improved as far as the entrepreneurial ecosystem is concerned. It involves the training sectors by the experienced and the skilled and successful entrepreneurs. Training makes the key aspect for creativity and innovation to assist in the productive entrepreneurial ecosystem. The enhancement of the small and medium enterprises through the enabling environment will be key. It is achieved through the flexible banking systems that are accessible to borrow and finance the small businesses to improve the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

3.4 Little Why

There has been increasing pressure from state and federal governments placed upon universities to improve their research commercialisation capabilities. This has manifested through federal and state budget announcements, which would lead us to assume that the government realises the inherent benefits of being an activator in this space (Zhou, 2021). Similarly, Faculty Engagement Manager Doctor Alex Thomson argues universities are willing to contribute solutions to the real-world facing problems though the fragmentation lies within connection to the industry (Appendix 1). Thomson claims that many companies aren't aware that they can approach universities with a problem or that the research they are interested in can be done for or with them by a university. Thus, we would suggest among our network of activators there lies a combination of realised and unrealised value.

Teece (1986) suggests, and as was pre-discussed, there are limits to a university-based strategy; other activators and complementary assets will be needed to improve research commercialisation. Governments, first of all, recognise Universities' role as drivers of economic development. They must simultaneously appreciate the critical role they must play to deliver successful outcomes in this space through funding and incentivising mutually beneficial research. Moreover, to better bridge the gap between Universities and industry, attracting more resourceful overseas venture capital firms may also be a helpful exercise (Ketchell, 2021).

While government support is necessary, it is redundant without universities' willingness to change and adapt their culture to accommodate the new need for academic entrepreneurialism. As Sadek (et al., 2015) states, the effectiveness of TTO's to support the commercialisation of research is directly related to the type of entrepreneurial ecosystem that is being projected from within the University itself. The financial impact of COVID-19 has seen Universities perform a vast array of budget cuts, including its faculty. Thus, to incentivise researchers at Universities more specifically, promotion and further tenure opportunities may be of particular interest (Siegel et al., 2003). Finally, it will take a combined effort from both University TTO's and Government to help bridge the gap between University and Industry not only on a national level but also globally.

There are many stakeholders who are beneficiaries of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, including the University of the Technology Sydney that produced baked students into the market. The productive ecosystem will absorb the products from the university (trained students) into the market. Therefore, the university gains in terms of the absorption of the students in the jobs. The board of directors of the Australian Bank will also benefit (O'Connor et al.,2018). It is accomplished in the sense when the entrepreneurial sector is saturated; many successful entrepreneurs will bring back their money into the bank for storage hence a benefit to the bank. Also, the bank will get to be promoted through the entire environment through the work that it does to the entire entrepreneurial ecosystem.

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